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TOX4 is a nuclear factor in young human HSC.

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We report here discovery of TOX4 as a nuclear factor in young human HSC with suspected rejuvenating potential.

Citations

1. Wang, L., Yu, J., Zhou, Q., Wang, X., Mukhanova, M., Du, W., Sun, L., Pajvani, U.B. and Accili, D., 2022. TOX4, an insulin receptor-independent regulator of hepatic glucose production, is activated in diabetic liver. *Cell metabolism*, 34(1), pp.158-170.